

PATHOLOGICAL ARBITRATION CLAUSE AS THE LEGAL BASIS OF INTERNATIONAL COMMERCIAL ARBITRATION

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ABSTRACT

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This article examines the issue of invalidity of an arbitration agreement, presents doctrinal approaches to this issue, examples from the practice of arbitration courts, and also developed recommendations for counterparties.

The purpose of the study was the question of the invalidity of the arbitration clause, which is relevant and remains open to discussion due to the lack of universal legal regulation of this problem. To study the problems of this aspect in international commercial arbitration, we will consider one of the grounds for invalidating an arbitration agreement – the nature and essence of the term «pathological arbitration clause».

Despite the fact that arbitration institutions publish standard arbitration clauses on their websites or include them in the text of their rules and this information is always publicly available, it often happens that the parties make mistakes when drafting an arbitration agreement, which may subsequently lead to its invalidity.

For the first time, the term «pathological arbitration clause» was introduced into the arbitration doctrine by Frederick Eismann in 1974, Secretary General of the Arbitration Court at the International Chamber of Commerce (currently the International Commercial Arbitration Court at the International Chamber of Commerce) to denote defective arbitration clauses or agreements. In order to determine which arbitration clause can be considered pathological, it was advisable to define the criteria for a «healthy» pathological clause. According to the study of F. Eismann's four main functions of a «healthy» arbitration clause are:

1. the generation of consequences binding on the parties (if there is no such condition, then the meaning of the existence of the arbitration agreement itself is lost);
2. exclusion of interference of national courts in the dispute resolution process, at least until the moment of the arbitration award (this condition guarantees the most important principles of arbitration – independence and impartiality);

3. empowering arbitrators to resolve disputes (due to their flexibility and the special procedure of this type of dispute resolution, the parties need to transfer the dispute resolution authority into the hands of professionals);

4. creating conditions for launching an effective arbitration procedure, culminating in the issuance of a decision subject to enforcement (the arbitration clause must contain information about the procedure chosen by the parties to resolve their dispute, as well as have provisions that the arbitration decision will be binding on both parties).

Despite the fact that almost 50 years have passed since the emergence of this concept, it remains applicable to arbitration agreements to this day and if an arbitration clause does not meet all these criteria at the same time, then it can be characterized as pathological, that is, a clause with gaps.

According to O.Y. Skvortsov, pathological arbitration agreements (reservations) should be considered such flaws in the agreement of the parties on the transfer of disputes to arbitration, which entail its invalidity¹. However, there are different approaches to the definition of a pathological clause, so, for example, O.Y. Skvortsov identifies the concepts of a pathological arbitration agreement and an arbitration agreement that can be invalidated for any reason. And V.V. Khvaley believes otherwise, saying that pathological arbitration agreements can only be called those whose invalidity entails the impossibility of their execution, which is expressed, for example:

- in pointing to a non-existent arbitration institution;
- in internal contradictions of the text of the arbitration agreement;
- in the absence of the competence of the arbitration institute on the dispute submitted for its consideration;
- in the impossibility of considering the case by the arbitrators specified in the arbitration agreement, etc.
- In addition, A.V. Popova notes that the pathology of arbitration clauses may be the result of:
 - uncertainties (if, for example, the arbitration clause does not allow the precise definition of the names of commercial arbitration);
 - incompleteness (if there is an insufficiently complete definition of the procedure for appointing arbitrators or the procedure for considering the case by arbitration);
 - loss of force (for example, if the parties have set a strict time frame for certain actions and the corresponding deadlines have already expired)².

As an example, we can cite the precedent described in paragraph 13 of the Review of Judicial and Arbitration Practice of Dispute Resolution in Cases involving foreign Persons³, when the State court declared the arbitration clause unenforceable, according to which all disputes had to be considered in the "Paris Institute", so neither the parties in this case nor

¹ Skvortsov O.Y. Arbitration proceedings of business disputes in Russia: problems, trends, prospects. M., 2005. p. 366.

² Popova A.V. The problem of pathological arbitration clauses in foreign trade contracts // Almanac of works of young scientists. 2003. N 1. p. 125.

³ Information Letter of the Presidium of the Supreme Arbitration Court of the Russian Federation dated February 16, 1998 No. 29 // VVAS RF. 1998. No. 4.

the state court could to determine which institutional arbitration is meant, the dispute was considered by the state court on the merits⁴.

It should be noted that the wording is not always too vague, which does not allow to establish a competent authority to consider a dispute between the parties, is the basis for recognizing an arbitration agreement as unenforceable. It is very important to consider not only the content of the arbitration agreement, but also to take into account the actions of the parties in the event of a dispute between them. For example, in a published precedent from the practice of Russian courts of general jurisdiction, the text of the contract contained an arbitration clause, according to which disputes had to be considered in the "arbitration commission of Moscow". Since there is no such body, there were all prerequisites for considering the dispute on the merits in a state court, but the plaintiff filed a claim with the IAC at the CCI of the Russian Federation, and the defendant in his objections to the claim did not put forward an argument that the IAC at the CCI of the Russian Federation had no jurisdiction to consider this dispute. Thus, the consolidation of the arbitration agreement was achieved in the form of an exchange of a statement of claim and a response to the claim, in which the plaintiff claims the existence of an arbitration agreement, and the defendant does not object to this in accordance with paragraph 2 of Article 7 of the UNCITRAL Model Law⁵.

Proceeding from the above, we define a pathological arbitration clause as a clause containing such flaws and inaccuracies that jeopardize the validity of this agreement and make it impossible for the parties to apply to arbitration to resolve the dispute that has arisen.

It is also necessary to consider what grounds for invalidating an arbitration agreement are established in countries with different legal systems. The approach of the English legislation is interesting, which specifies the requirements for an arbitration agreement and includes:

- number of arbitrators (section 15 of the Arbitration Act 1996);
- the procedure for their appointment, including the procedure for the appointment of the Chairman (section 16 (1));
- Qualifications required for these arbitrators (Section 24)⁶.
- In the absence of these requirements in the arbitration agreement, there is a risk of its invalidation.

In Georgia, the legislation contains an indication that "an arbitration agreement must contain:

- name of the parties,
- addresses of their place of residence or location;
- subject of dispute;
- date and place of conclusion of the contract"⁷.

In this case, the existence of the arbitration agreement itself is important, it is not necessary to specify the type of arbitration, arbitrators, the chosen procedure of the

⁴ Karabelnikov B. R. International Commercial Arbitration. Textbook. 2nd edition, 2013, p. 132.

⁵ Bulletin of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation. 2000. No. 7. p. 8.

⁶ URL: <https://iqdecision.com/arbitrazh-v-velikobritanii/>

⁷ The Law of Georgia "On Private Arbitration" of 12.04.1997

proceedings, since these issues can be discussed and established by the parties in the event of a dispute as a separate agreement.

In Lithuania, "an arbitration agreement may be declared invalid in court at the request of one of the parties on the general grounds of invalidation of transactions or upon finding a violation of the requirements established by law"⁸.

The study showed that the legislation of many countries does not contain direct rules containing grounds for the recognition of arbitration clauses due to the presence of pathologies. However, almost all countries follow the principle of autonomy of the arbitration agreement with respect to the main contract. For example, Federal Law No. 382-FZ of December 29, 2015 "On Arbitration (Arbitration Proceedings) in the Russian Federation" in Article 16. establishes that the arbitration court may itself decide on its competence, including on any objections regarding the existence or validity of the arbitration agreement. An arbitration clause that is part of the contract is recognized as an agreement that does not depend on other terms of the contract. The adoption of an arbitration decision that the contract is invalid does not in itself entail the invalidity of the arbitration agreement. The Republic of Azerbaijan is unanimous in this with the Russian Federation, in accordance with Article 16. According to the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On International Arbitration", an arbitration clause that is part of a contract should be interpreted as an agreement that does not depend on other terms of the contract. The decision of the arbitration court on the invalidity of the contract does not entail the "ipso jure" invalidity of the arbitration clause. The legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan also respects the principle of autonomy in Article 21. The Law "On International Commercial Arbitration" dated February 16, 2021⁹. The same approach is followed by countries with a very developed arbitration practice, such as France, Canada and England.

Next, we will consider cases when it is possible to recognize an arbitration clause as pathological. The analysis of frequently occurring reservations with drawbacks showed frequently formulated types of arbitration pathologies:

- the arbitration institute is named incorrectly or does not exist at all. Such an error leads to the fact that the arbitration agreement cannot be executed and the consequence is that the parties need to apply to the state court of the country for the resolution of their dispute, which does not always turn out to be beneficial for both parties to the contract.

- if the arbitration agreement provides for both arbitration as a method of dispute resolution and the jurisdiction of state courts. Even if this contradicts the fourth point of the "correct" Eisman arbitration clause, there are cases when it is possible to combine both methods of dispute resolution. For example, if the plaintiff filed an application to the state court, and the defendant did not object, then this dispute falls under the jurisdiction of the chosen court.

- if one arbitration institution is indicated as the place of dispute resolution, and the rules of another arbitration institution are chosen as the dispute resolution procedure.

⁸ Law of the Republic of Lithuania of April 2, 1996 No. i-1274 "On Commercial Arbitration" // URL: <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalActPrint/lt?jfwid=wd7z6aul4&documentId=TAIS.462446&category=TAD>

⁹ Law of The Republic of Uzbekistan "On International Commercial Arbitration" of February 16, 2021 // <https://lex.uz/docs/5294087#5296680>

Despite the fact that the rules of arbitration institutions at first glance seem very similar, however, each of them has its own characteristics, in particular, each arbitration has its own organizational structure, which may radically differ from the structure of the arbitration rules chosen by the parties. Also, it is worth noting that almost all existing arbitration institutions conduct proceedings only in accordance with their rules.

- specifying the names of the arbitrators may also serve as an obstacle to resolving the dispute between the parties, since it is impossible to guess exactly when the dispute will arise, therefore, the arbitrator at that time may not be able to participate in this dispute.

However, it should be considered that there are cases when the court can "reanimate", that is, save a pathological arbitration clause by removing from it the very provision that could lead to its recognition as invalid. Proceeding from this, we note that despite the presence of defects in the arbitration agreement, international arbitration bodies always tend to such an interpretation of pathology that would make possible the execution of the arbitration agreement.

It would be advisable to specify recommendations that will help to avoid the above pathologies in the arbitration agreement between the counterparties:

- 1) the reservation should be formulated clearly and in as much detail as possible, it is necessary to make sure that the specified information is correct;
- 2) when drafting an arbitration agreement, the parties must always comply with the four points recommended by Eisman in order to avoid the presence of defects in the agreement;
- 3) it is necessary to refer to the model clauses that are widely available, in particular, it would be more effective to use the model clause of the chosen arbitration institution;
- 4) it should be borne in mind that disputes that may arise between the parties cannot be predicted, therefore it is not necessary to limit the arbitration agreement in this regard, it is better not to specify on which disputes this clause should be applied.
- 5) it is not necessary to specify one arbitration institution, but to choose the rules of another arbitration institution as a dispute resolution procedure;
- 6) it is necessary to refuse to indicate the names of arbitrators for the above reasons.

Summing up this study, we note the importance of the parties' awareness of the correct arbitration clause, its content and mandatory conditions, which subsequently will not become a stumbling block in resolving disputes between the parties, but will only contribute to a quick, clear and effective consideration of the case in international arbitration centers.

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